

FACTORS THAT RECEIVED MARRIAGE AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE POWER OF MARRIAGE

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Annotasia

This article reveals the importance of forming visions of various aspects of matrimonial maturity (physiological, sexual, economic, spiritual, social, psychological) as well as factors of matrimonial acquisition, perceptions of family life and influence on family strength, and the age of marriage, characteristics of marriage motives, dates and conditions of pre-marriage dating.

Keywords: maturation into marriage, sex education, family life, marital motives, sex legal, economic, spiritual-moral, psychological, physiological aspects, clinical observations, puberty, sexual imbalance of the couple, feelings of love, trust and respect.

The so-called sacred space of the family, the strength of the "family castle" depends on the characteristics of the factors that received the marriage, the foundation of this castle, on how correctly and firmly they are laid. If this foundation is mature, solid, then the castle built on it will also be showy, light, which will give comfort, calmness, peace, comfort to those who live in it.

Just as no wall or house is without a foundation, your family to build has its own foundations. They are the factors that led to the emergence, construction of the same family.

If the influence of the factors of the receipt of this marriage on the occurrence of the family is inappropriate, if it is built in a hurry, empty, oblique, the wall of the family gesture mounted on it will also continue to be crooked and savings, and it risks that the same castle will come and fall one day, break down. A castle built on such a foundation cannot bring peace, peace, joy to those who live in it, even if it does not collapse, break down. They constantly have to live in some kind of anxiety, to be scared of, discomfort, embarrassment. So what are these foundations that are the factors that got a marriage? As we go about the factors of the matrimonial marriage, it is worth noting that the factors of the matrimonial marriage consist of a complex of multifaceted factors, which embody many social, economic, biological, physiological, spiritual, moral and psychological factors that are the basis for the occurrence of this or that marriage, and determine to what extent The most important thing here is to what extent these young people can meet family life, marriage requirements.

Features of maturation in marriage

The concept of maturation in marriage is also, in turn, an extremely complex and relative concept. Because a person is a being who is constantly developing and improving, achieving regular new heights in his professional activity or spiritual and moral development. If a person is divided into those who talk about their "full maturity" to this or that activity, then this means that he has reached a certain limit and it is impossible to develop further. That is why the concept of "maturity" cannot be literally appropriate when it comes to the

maturation of a person into marriage or any activity. That is why this concept is used only in the quality of a certain universally accepted standard, average norm, a certain conditional "unit of measure", indicators, etc., when talking about the "maturity" of a person, especially marriage, family life. For example, for all educational institutions (school, Lyceum, College, institutes), graduation exams (such as the state examination system, diploma work protection systems) will be available, and with them it will be possible to analyze the sum of the average knowledge and qualifications acquired by graduates. This gives them a certain right that they can then continue their studies again or work in a particular specialty. From this point of view, "maturity" - serves as an indicator that determines the qualitative and quantitative characteristic of a certain stage, Phase, threshold of development in a certain maturity.

The question of the maturity of a person to marriage and family life is an indicator of an It is feared that the factors of those cited that received a marriage in their own way are problems of a more complex nature. In the psychological literature, which is devoted to highlighting the social psychological problems of the family of the present time, different forms and manifestations of nikoq Oldi factors are distinguished. Below we bring to your attention information about some of them. individual character, which cannot be measured by any strict norm of extreme complexity..

Among the factors that got married are the young people who are starting this family: their motives for starting a family: the conditions and circumstances of the dating period until they start a family (how long they know each other): they can be included in the family as a consolation. striving for their future family life. Of course, each of these factors can have a different character at a different age, while each of them, in turn, is divided into several more types.

For example, when marriage is called mature, the family is formed by young people: physical (physiological), sexual. legal. economic. spiritual-moral. aspects of maturity such as psychological can be differentiated. Among these, the indicators of legal, sexual maturity are characterized by the fact that they have sufficiently pronounced symptoms, signs and there are aspects in the relevant legal, medical, psychological literature that are given a lot of Information, economic, spiritual and moral, psychological aspects are somewhat more complex, have a strict indicator, have no limits.

For example, when marriage is called maturation of the family-building youth: physical (physiological), sexual. legal. economic. spiritual-moral. aspects of maturity such as psychological can be differentiated. Among these, the indicators of legal, sexual maturity are characterized by the fact that they have sufficiently pronounced symptoms, signs and there are aspects about which a lot of information is given in the relevant legal, medical, psychological literature, while the economic, spiritual and moral, psychological aspects are a little more complex, have a strict indicator, do not have a limit.

The sexual maturity of a person has its own factors. According to clinical observations, in modern girls, sexual maturity (puberty) falls between the ages of 12-14, and in boys-between 14-16. Of course, this maturity can occur earlier in some individuals and later in others. These indicators may vary by 2 years. Some medical scientists believe that it will take another 2-3 years for children to be fully sexually mature.

Sexual maturity leads to the formation of strict sexual needs. By this period, children begin to show secondary sexual symptoms. The activity of the sex secretion glands increases. Monthly

cycles (menstruation) in girls, pollutions in boys begin to occur. In other words, a pubertal period begins in them. (A detailed account of this period and its features is given in topic 4). So by this period, in addition to the growing material and spiritual interests of children, sexual needs count from strong sources of personality activity, which begins to manifest itself in various psychological and social forms.

The occurrence of sexual predisposition, sexual need is a specific stage in the fact that a person begins to develop biologically. They have a great influence on the development of the child's psyche, the formation of his personality, other aspects of life activity.

Many problems of sex life will have to be explained not only to young people, but also to adults who have been married for a long time, have children, since many serious conflicts can also arise on this basis. The issue of sexual relations is a sensitive issue, in which "false, Bachelor shyness" is often encountered. Some parents and teachers even Māori leaders object to the issue of sex education at school, and "all the necessary information on sex education, gender issues is given in biology courses, on top of which "our ancestors lived like binoys even without such sexual literacy", - meditated in the tribe. Of course, such a point of view is rather backward, today it is conclusions that are made without taking into account the requirements of marriage-family relations, the functions of the Modern Family. It is in such ways that the importance of any sanitary and hygienic whitening information that gives young people on such sensitive and necessary issues as sexual education is completely underestimated. This is due to the fact that millions of adolescents remain absent during puberty and, as a result, make irreparable mistakes in life in some cases.

Anxiety, to be scared of which is not justified by anything, and sometimes on the ground of real panic, various deviations, neuromuscular disorders can occur in adolescent behavior. All this is the result of the fact that sanitary and hygienic education is not well established and sexual education is not provided. This issue is an issue that has a very serious essence, especially in our Ethnos.

The issue of sex education is often considered either in the form of an issue that does not require special attention and does not cause any difficulties, which can be easily mastered for each age group, or extremely personal, intimate, which cannot be discussed among many, especially among children. Similar considerations led to the exclusion of sexual education materials, related activities, from the school program in a number of countries, especially in the former Union. In this regard, it is advisable to consider sexual rearing in a way that is inextricably linked with the sanitary-hygienic, psychogenetic information that every person today needs to master, know about the functioning of the organism.

And in family life, having knowledge of the psychology of sex life is an issue of extreme importance. In a comprehensive analysis of the data provided by various specialists, it can be said that in every fourth divorced couple (in 29% of divorces), a violation of sexual musicality in one way or another (sexual imbalance of couple is the cause).

Of course, feelings of mutual love, trust and respect, feelings of commonality of interests and intentions arose at short intervals, and, accordingly, the knowledge of the psychology of sex life for couples who have an urgent family may not be able to help on their own. At such a speed, families that have occurred at a short time (as early as a week or two through matchmakers, relatives) are especially increasing among representatives of our nationalities in recent years. Without a complex of likes and positive emotional feelings of young people towards each other, the effect of these bi-LIMS will be low. They coordinate the intimate life of

the couple only in cases where the couple liked each other, attractive to each other. On the other hand, it is also not necessary to give up the problems of the psycho hygiene of sexual life in marriage as some kind of "unkempt, shameful thing". Because, in most cases, scientific knowledge in the field of psycho hygiene of sex life can help young couple get rid of the sad mistakes that can be allowed and thus maintain their own marriage. Thus, sexual maturity is a phenomenon in which the anatomy and physiology of a person is sufficiently clear and clear from the point of view. However, its psychological, moral aspects are extremely complex. That is why, when a person is called sexual maturity in marriage, referring to its physiological punctuation, knows the full essence of sexual maturity, in addition, it is necessary for a person to have both the necessary scientific psychological knowledge and the right perceptions in relation to the psychogenesis of sexual life. This is a process that undoubtedly requires special attention, special training, training. In addition to the issue of sexual maturity of young people to marriage, several other types of social maturity can be distinguished, as mentioned above. These are: sexual, civil, professional, socio-economic, spiritual, moral and psychological maturity. Among these, the sexual (physiological) maturity of young people is realized much earlier than in others, we will dwell below on what other set of problems may arise in connection with these issues. Civil. legal maturity is determined by the legal age of puberty of this person, by the fact that he is legally considered a person who has the right to build a family, have children. In our country, this is indicated as 18 years old. At this time, he will be able to enjoy all the rights and mandatory-yachts established in the Constitution. Age 18 can be considered the legal maturity age of a person. Professional maturity is also a much more complex concept. Its complexity is that, on the one hand, it is determined by the completion of some kind of educational institution, training courses, that is, by having the special knowledge necessary to carry out a certain type of work. However, a person after graduating from one or another educational institution (College, Lyceum, Technical School, Institute) will have to work for several years in the profession of his choice, and only then it is possible to talk about his occupation.

At the same time, it is possible to achieve professional maturity in some professions as early as the age of 19-20, while in others, for example, in the surgeon-Doctor, this can be achieved when he reaches the age of 29-30 later. Another aspect of personality maturity is socio-economic maturity. It implies that a person can provide for himself and his own family independently financially. Of particular importance in the family development of young people is their economic independence. In this place, too, there are different age limits, young people, some of whom, as early as 18-19 years old, can achieve economic independence from their parents' family, while others, even at the age of 25-30, use the financial support of their fathers.

Among these maturation aspects, it is most complicated to talk about the spiritual and moral maturity of an individual. Because a clear criterion and description of this aspect has not yet been developed.

Thus, the concept of "maturity" embodies many aspects in itself. It is worth mentioning that the concept of "maturity" is necessarily inextricably linked with a certain life experience, that is, with "vital knowledge". There are also specific individual characteristics of "mastering vital knowledge", passing through "life universities". Someone "gets to know life well" when they are 20 years old, and someone remains in childhood even at 30 years old. This is influenced by the existing social conditions, the public and the social order. It is known that in previous

times, especially during the war years, children experienced life difficulties that even adults could not cope with all the time. At that time, children from 1214 years old helped their mothers to support the family. Also, those children who live in urban and rural areas, with few children and many children, growing up in nuclear or multi-class families, also contribute to the material, social security of the family, the duration and amount of work involved in these activities are different. Knowing life, life experiences can be carried out at different speeds in different individuals, and it is absolutely impossible to show some kind of age, time frame in this place. On top of that, knowing life, the surrounding world that surrounds us, is in turn endless. Nevertheless, it is possible to establish certain minimum limits of social and economic maturity, that is, there is such a life experience, a "minimum" of knowledge, without which it is impossible to consider any age, a young man, to be literally mature. Here is how broad the concept of self-sufficient "maturity" of the above is. Again we are obliged to use it. Because it embodies important conditions, situations that determine the strength of marriage.

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